

1 Identification of the Branching Order within the Kingdom *Bamfordvirae*

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21 Text S1

22 **Materials and Methods**

23 **Sequence selection.** After the accumulation of a redundant pool of viral homologs, we constructed
24 the LG (+ accessories) preliminary trees, which were examined for detecting violations of monophyly
25 of established viral clades (nesting of a clade or viral sequence with known taxonomic affiliation in
26 the phylogenetically distinct clade) and removed all sequences violating monophyly of any viral clade.
27 Thus, we removed the results of potential horizontal transfers or homoplasies from further analysis.
28 If a taxon had two or more homologs that did not violate the monophyly of other viral clades, we
29 examined alignments to detect plesiomorphies and apomorphies among the viral homologs and
30 outgroup under study and retained the viral homologs in which plesiomorphies were not substituted,
31 and apomorphies were best represented. In some cases, however, the topological relationships of
32 homologs were of interest, and we retained both or more homologs in alignment (for instance, the
33 D6/D11 helicases). We also removed from alignments identical sequences presented in GenBank
34 under different accessions. We carried out the same selection procedure for sequences of cellular
35 origin.

36 **Multiple sequence alignment.** We employed a multi-step alignment strategy. a) Viral genera,
37 families, or genera/family-level clades were aligned using the gap open 2 and gap extend 0 or 1 options
38 (MUSCLE). In the next step, we removed all positions in which more than 10% of the sequences had
39 gaps. Further, the alignment process was repeated using the gap open 1 and gap extend 0 options
40 (MUSCLE). Then, alignment positions with more than 10% gaps were removed. b) To create NCLDV
41 alignments, ready-aligned genera/family blocks were combined and aligned using the gap open 2 and
42 gap extend 0 or 1 options. c) To create alignment blocks of cellular organisms, the same approach was
43 used, except that instead of genera and families the archaeal and bacterial phyla or the eukaryotic

44 *Animalia (ParaHoxozoa, Bilateria), Fungi, Oomycota, Archaeplastida, and Kinetoplastida* clades
45 were initially aligned. Then prokaryotic phyla or eukaryotic clades were combined and aligned using
46 the gap open 2 and gap extend 0 or 1 options. d) Finally, depending on the goals of the final MUSCLE,
47 MAFFT, or MUSCLE v5 alignments, the pre-aligned viral and cellular blocks were combined and
48 aligned. For the final MUSCLE alignments building, we used the gap open 2 or 3 and the gap extend
49 0 or 1 options. For the MAFFT final alignments building, we used matrix none or BLOSUM30, gap
50 open 1, and gap extension 0.0001 penalties. The choice of the MAFFT matrix was carried out
51 depending on the preservation of anchor amino acid substitutions of alignments, published in the
52 literature. In the case of MUSCLE v5, we used the mpc algorithm under the permutation and
53 perturbation parameters by default. For the MUSCLE, MAFFT, or MUSCLE v5 algorithms, positions
54 with more than 40% gaps were removed.

55 **Determination of the root position.** The root position of the individual protein trees and
56 dendrograms, concatenated trees, supertree, and superdendrogram could be pinpointed due to the
57 presence of eukaryotic homologs, as well as their viral homologs (Family B DNA polymerase, DNA-
58 directed RNA polymerase subunit α (RNAP α), DNA-directed RNA polymerase subunit β (RNAP β),
59 mRNA capping enzyme, Topoisomerase II, D5-like primase, PCNA, TFIIB, and Metallopeptidase
60 WLM). Many of these viral genes are of eukaryotic (protoeukaryotic) or eukaryotic
61 (protoeukaryotic)/archaeal origin (2). Similar, the root position could be pinpointed for proteins of
62 viral (D6/D11 helicase), bacterial, or bacteriophage/plasmid origin (FtsK-HerA superfamily ATPase,
63 AP (apurinic) endonuclease family 2, Holliday junction resolvase (RuvC), Uracil-DNA glycosylase,
64 and Superfamily III (SFIII) helicase) (2, 8, 52). Of the 14 proteins (genes) of cellular origin (Table
65 S6), 9 are of eukaryotic/protoeukaryotic origin, and 5 are of bacterial origin. We rooted these trees in
66 the following way. Trees containing the multifamily and multiple type proteins (PolB, RNAP α ,
67 RNAP β , HerA-FtsK ATPase) were rooted according to the branching order of the cellular clades

68 (*Archaea*, *Bacteria*, and *Eukaryota*) as in published data (22, 38-39, 52-53, 90). The remaining trees
69 with non-multifamily and non-multiple type proteins were rooted according to the branching order of
70 cellular clades presented in the literature if clades of more than one cellular domain were present. For
71 instance, trees containing *Archaea*, *Bacteria*, and *Eukaryota* were rooted between *Bacteria* and
72 *Archaea*. Alternatively, trees, dendrograms, concatenated trees, supertree, and superdendrogram
73 (topologies with only one domain as an outgroup) were rooted between the viral and cellular clades.
74 Topologies without outgroup were rooted according to the topologies of the corresponding proteins
75 where outgroup was present. Topologies of “synapomorphic” proteins were rooted according to the
76 branching orders of NCLDV identified for trees with outgroups.

77 **Prediction of three-dimensional structures of proteins using ColabFold.** To exclude from the
78 analysis amino acid regions that gave an unreliable prediction (pLDDT < 70) we established the
79 following criterion. In the predicted structures, the total length of regions with pLDDT < 70 embedded
80 in the regions with the pLDDT > 70 had not to exceed 20 % of the total length of prediction, otherwise
81 the alignment was considered unsuitable for prediction. This criterion was applied to individual sets
82 of predictions of *Eukaryota*, *Bacteria*, NCLDV, and *Preplasmiviricota*, but not to individual
83 predictions since this criterion refers to the applicability of the alignment. If an amino acid region with
84 the pLDDT < 70 (for more than half of family/clade members), with a length exceeding 20% of the
85 total length of prediction, flanked the prediction, then such amino acid region was removed from the
86 alignment. If such a region fell inside the alignment, then we built an alignment of another fragment
87 of the same protein.

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